

Project Title	Digital ecosystem for the New European Bauhaus initiative
Project Acronym	digiNEB
Project Number	101083743
Type of project	Digital Europe Programme (DIGITAL)
Topics	DIGITAL-2021-DEPLOY-01-BAUHAUS
Starting date of Project	1 October 2022
Duration of the project	27 months
Website	https://digiNEB.eu

D5.3 – DigiNEB Deployment Roadmap

Work Package	WP5 Outreach, roadmap and sustainability
Task	T5.3 DigiNEB Deployment Roadmap
Lead author	Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)
Contributors	Diana Popa (TU Delft)
Peer reviewer	Roberto Cavallo (EAAE) Mar Muñoz Aparici (EAAE)
Quality Officer	Florence Kuijl (InnovaWood)
Version	V1.0
Due Date	30.11.2024
Submission Date	10.02.2025

Dissemination Level

X	PU: Public
	SEN: Sensitive
	R-UE/EU-R: EU Classified
	C-UE/EU-C: EU Classified
	S-UE/EU-S: EU Classified

Versioning History

Revision	Date	Editors	Comments
0.6	08/10/2024	Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)	First draft
0.7	04/02/2025	Mar / Roberto (EAAE)	Peer review
0.8	05/02/2024	Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)	Final draft
0.9	10/02/2025	Florence Kuijl (InnovaWood)	Quality Control
1.0	10/02/2025	Frank van der Hoeven (TU Delft)	Final version

Glossary of terms

Item	Description
ACE	Architects’ Council of Europe
AEC	Architecture, Engineering, and Construction
AI	Artificial Intelligence
Dataspace	Framework that supports data sharing within a data ecosystem
EAAE	European Association for Architectural Education
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EuroPass	EU initiative to increase transparency of qualifications and mobility of citizens in Europe
HE	Higher Education
Micro-credentials	Micro-credentials certify the learning outcomes of short-term learning experiences, for example a short course or training
NEB	New European Bauhaus
NEBA	New European Bauhaus Alliance
OER	Open Educational Resources

Keywords

Roadmap, NEB, Digital Literacy, Digitalisation.

Disclaimer

DigiNEB has received funding from the European Commission’s Digital Europe funding programme under Grant Agreement no. 101083743. The content of this document does not represent the opinion of the European Commission, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that might be made of such content.

Executive Summary

The **New European Bauhaus (NEB)** is a European Union initiative aimed at transforming the design, planning, and construction of living environments to make the green transition enjoyable, attractive, and accessible for all. The **DigiNEB project** supports this vision by bridging the digital and NEB communities, creating a pan-European digital ecosystem to promote EU digital solutions for greener, more inclusive living spaces. DigiNEB focuses on raising awareness, fostering collaboration, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of digital tools and methods within the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) sector.

DigiNEB outlines in this context a roadmap to ensure the long-term impact of its initiatives, emphasising the transfer of methods and tools to stakeholders. The roadmap aligns with the NEB Academy, which aims to upskill and reskill the construction ecosystem for a regenerative, bio-based, and circular economy.

Roadmap for Digital Literacy in NEB

The NEB Academy will serve as the central hub for collecting, supervising, and developing courses and training programs to support the Green Transition. To address fragmentation and ensure accessibility, the following steps are recommended based on the experience of DigiNEB:

1. **NEB Course Base:** Establish a certified repository of courses and training options to unify offerings across the EU.
2. **EU Dataspace for Open Educational Resources (OER):** Create a centralised infrastructure to share, mix, and reuse OER, integrating them into local Learning Management Systems.
3. **Integration of Digital and AI Literacy:** Integrate digital and AI literacy into professional titles like "architect," pushing higher education institutions to include these skills in their curricula.
4. **EU Micro-Credentials:** Implement a standardised system for micro-credentials (3–30 ECTS) to certify lifelong learning, ensuring recognition across EU member states.
5. **Open Badges / EuroPass:** Develop a standardised system for digital badges or certifications to validate micro-credentials and skills acquired through lifelong learning.
6. **Financing Mechanism for Lifelong Learning:** Establish funding mechanisms similar to those for traditional education to support lifelong learning initiatives.
7. **Course Localisation:** Support the translation and adaptation of courses to local languages and regional specifications to ensure accessibility across the EU.
- 8.

Timeline for Digital Literacy Roadmap:

- **2020–2025:** Launch the NEB Academy Alliance and pilot micro-credentials.
- **2025–2030:** Develop the NEB course base, EU dataspace for OER, and Open Badges/EuroPass system.
- **2030–2035:** Implement EU-wide micro-credentials and funding mechanisms for lifelong learning.

Roadmap for Digitalisation in NEB

To support the NEB's digital transformation, the following actions are proposed:

1. **Cascading NEB Grants:** Allocate funding to smaller NEB stakeholders through cascading grants, enabling them to participate in EU-funded projects.
2. **Open-Source Requirement:** Mandate that digital tools developed through EU funding be open-source, unless restricted by knowledge security concerns.
3. **E-Learning and Citizen Platforms:** Fast-track the development of open-source platforms for e-learning and citizen engagement (e.g., co-planning and local democracy tools).
4. **Digital Workflows:** Focus on developing and teaching workflows how multiple tools sequentially can meet specific objectives, alongside separate tool development.
5. **Discovery Support:** Enhance the dissemination of EU-funded projects by training participants in (digital) outreach and networking with local governments, NGOs, and market players.
6. **Horizon Software Space:** Establish a Git repository for hosting and developing digital solutions from EU-funded projects.
7. **Interoperability:** Require EU-funded projects to address the full complexity of NEB principles (beauty, sustainability, inclusion) and ensure interoperability between tools.

Timeline for Digitalisation Roadmap:

- **2020–2025:** Launch DigiNEB and initiate cascading grants.
- **2025–2030:** Develop open-source e-learning and citizen platforms, enforce open-source and interoperability requirements for EU-funded projects.
- **2030–2035:** Focus on digital workflows and establish the Horizon software space.

Conclusion

DigiNEB's digital literacy and digitalisation roadmaps aim to create a cohesive, sustainable, and inclusive ecosystem for the AEC sector. By addressing gaps in funding, accessibility, interoperability, and digital skills, these roadmaps will support the EU's Green Deal and ensure the long-term success of the NEB initiative through the continuation in the NEB Academy. The integration of open education, micro-credentials, and open-source solutions will empower stakeholders to drive the green transition effectively.

Table of Contents

Glossary of terms	3
Keywords.....	3
Disclaimer.....	3
Executive Summary.....	4
Table of Contents	6
1. Background and Policy Context.....	7
Observatory and Toolkit.....	7
2. Gap analysis	9
Preliminary gap analysis report [4].....	9
Analysis.....	9
Gaps	10
Final gap analysis report [5]	11
3. NEB Academy	13
4. Policy Context	14
5. Challenges	17
6. Roadmap digital literacy NEB.....	18
Timeline of recommendations to the European Commission.....	19
Timeline of recommendations to the EU member states	19
7. Roadmap digitalisation NEB.....	20
Timeline of recommendations to the European Commission.....	21
Timeline of recommendations to the EU member states	21
8. Conclusion.....	22
List of Figures	24
References	24

1. Background and Policy Context

The New European Bauhaus (NEB) seeks to transform the way we design, plan, and build the environments we live as...

“a policy and funding initiative that makes green transition in built environments enjoyable, attractive and convenient for all.”

In that context, the objective of the DigiNEB project is to bridge...

“the digital and NEB communities and raise awareness around EU digital solutions for all NEB stakeholders, establishing a pan-European digital ecosystem. With its lean action plan, digiNEB.eu enables Europe’s Green Deal ambition in designing & building greener and more inclusive living spaces for a better quality of life.” [1]

The ambition of enabling ‘Europe’s Green Deal’ requires that we focus on a broader audience than just the NEB community. This is reflected in the EC’s definition of the so-called NEB Academy, which specifically refers to the ‘construction ecosystem’. It implies that the full architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) sector participates.

Within the DigiNEB project work a **“DigiNEB.eu Deployment Roadmap,”** is included as the output of **“T5.3 Sustainability Roadmap”**.

*“This task will develop and deliver a policy and sustainability plan that will leverage the project’s results to the European and national policy level to ensure continued impact. The task will define the long-term sustainability approach by ensuring that all methods and instruments are transferred to the relevant stakeholder groups for continued use. As part of the stakeholder engagement and outreach strategy, policy material will be created, including a NEB Digital Roadmap. The roadmap will **identify gaps and obstacles** and will develop recommendations stemming from the DigiNEB.eu **Observatory and Toolkit** addressing such gaps or issues that prevent the development of digital solutions for NEB.” [2]*

Observatory and Toolkit

The assignment above mentions specifically the so-called “observatory” and the “toolkit”. Both the Toolkit and the Observatory are part of the innovation mapping activities (Pillar I) of the DigiNEB project.

DigiNEB will consistently analyse and map actions and outcomes supported by EU programmes including Horizon 2020, CEF Telecom, Creative Europe, Structural Funds projects, and many others. The main result is a comprehensive online catalogue of initiatives and a digital toolkit providing easy access to the whole suite of collected IT-driven outputs and solutions. [3]

Toolkit

The toolkit is described as *“a comprehensive online catalogue of initiatives and a digital toolkit providing easy access to the whole suite of collected IT-driven outputs and solutions.”*

Observatory

The observatory is loosely described as a *“birds-eye view of the complete collection of EU-funded projects in the NEB space”*.

While it is not specifically mentioned in the definition of Pillar I, by its own definition the Observatory is strongly aligned with the comprehensive online catalogue of initiatives.

Because ‘toolkit’ and ‘observatory’ are ambivalent terms, we choose to use in the case of the online platform categories like: Digital Tools and Digital Projects (please note that digital projects do develop often one or more tools).

In the case that digital projects were specifically funded as NEB initiatives, we have labelled them accordingly: NEB Labs, EIT Community NEB, ERDF innovative actions, NEB Prize winners, and NEB in Horizon Europe.

2. Gap analysis

The preliminary gaps analysis and the final gaps analysis both list extensive lists of gaps or issues that not just prevent the development of digital solutions (an emphasis in the preliminary report). DigiNEB also reports on the gaps that prevent the uptake of such solutions (an emphasis in the final report).

Preliminary gap analysis report [4]

Based on the desktop analysis of the digital tools and projects, the preliminary report compiled a graph, representing the landscape of tools and solutions by using two axes: the level of openness and the size of the developer:

- to what extent is a developing party willing to adopt the EU approach of open science, open access and open source?
- what is the size of the developer (or the project initiative): are we dealing with a micro-enterprise or a larger consortium of well-established institutes and multinationals?

LANDSCAPE CLUSTERING

Figure 1 - Positioning the digital projects/tools on two axes: openness and developer size. Horizontally, you will find the developer size, with larger Horizon Europe consortia on the left and micro-enterprises and individual developers on the right. Vertically, you will find the level of accessibility and openness, with open-source tools listed in well-adopted repositories at the top and standalone websites lacking proper access to software output at the bottom

Analysis

Large / Extra Large

Among our initial collection, *Horizon Europe projects* and *Community Engagement projects* were among the project with the largest developers/consortia.

Hard to access and not sustainable

Horizon Europe projects and *AI projects* appear to be the least open. The observation that Horizon projects appear to be among the least open may seem to contradict the official policies of the EU and deserve a further explanation:

Indeed, the publications and official deliverables that result from EU-projects are often available as open access. However, the digital tools or solutions they have produced are hard to find, difficult to access, often not developed or provided as open-source. More than once we found that the websites setup over the course of a project were no longer maintained after the project was completed. The corresponding online resources become rather quickly dysfunctional and some already disappeared altogether within the timespan of our project after we had listed them in our directories.

Medium-sized / Small /Extra Small

The developers of *Parametric tools* and *AI projects* in the field of architecture and design are in size close to the size of a typical architectural office: the majority is small to very small with some exceptions.

Open-sourced

Community engagement tools and *parametric design tools* tend to be the most open tools often providing their work as open-source solutions.

Gaps

While this simplification has its limitations, it helped us in identifying gaps that need to be addressed. When considering the growing collection of digital tools, solutions and projects, we observed the following gaps:

Gap 1: Funding

We do find digital tool development among architects, designers, and civic organisations as part of the NEB community. However, there seems to be a poor fit with EU programming. Few, if any, of these developed tools declare support from EU-funded projects. Given the predominantly micro-enterprise structure of the architectural design sector, there seems to be a mismatch with the complex and large calls in the Horizon programs.

Smaller lumpsum or cascading funding, with reduced administrative burdens, might bridge this gap.

Gap 2: Accessibility

While the majority of developers of parametric design tools and participatory tools for citizens have adopted the principle of open (source) software, the tools produced in the EU supported projects are either not easily accessible or not accessible at all.

This gap could be closed if the EU would provide a Git platform where projects are required to make their work available for use and further development.

Gap 3: Findability

The field has many overviews of digital tools relevant to the NEB community, but these are dispersed across various online locations. Locating these resources and making the best use of them is quite challenging.

Gap 4: Integration

The NEB is founded on three key principles: aesthetics, sustainability, and inclusion. While we were able to identify tools in each of these fields, integrating these tools is a different story. Tools that try to balance all NEB priorities at the same time are rare or even non-existent.

Final gap analysis report [5]

Below we highlight a key selection of the gaps reported in the second and final DigiNEB gap analysis report. In that report the aspect of digital and AI literacy surfaces as an important gap that should be bridged. Other gaps are:

- long term sustainability of the incentivised initiatives;
- limited impact of the citizen centred initiatives by Horizon Europe;
- a lacking overview of solutions;
- interoperability;
- lack of visibility of NEB to the majority of citizens;
- lack of critical thinking;
- lacking standards for bio-based materials;
- several digital tools/solutions are not affordable for micro enterprises, such as architects.

Digitalisation gaps

- Volumes of digital solutions become cumbersome for users who, while lacking a systematised solution or quality filter for choosing the right tool for their needs, have to navigate through repetitive information sources and alternatives that bring no decisive edge for quickly choosing a solution.
- A helicopter overview of existing solutions is either lacking or not visible enough inside the practitioner's community.
- Initiatives on digitalisation should not be limited to the conceptual, construction or repurposing phases. They should also include data capture during post-occupancy in order to make living spaces continuously adaptive environments.
- Innovation in silos is another challenge, with upscaling of solutions becoming difficult.
- With the diversification of available digital solutions, the challenge of interoperability becomes greater and greater.
- An additional factor that hinders interoperability is the high cost of switching between digital solutions or solution providers.

Digital solutions for Civic engagement gaps

- There is discrepancy across the EU landscape regarding the use of technologies for enabling citizen engagement showing fragmentation in practices and, we might argue, the fact that visibility of certain initiatives is hindered by the combination of high volume and small scale of these initiatives.
- Similar to the perception on the limited impact that Horizon Europe has, projects developed for encouraging citizen centred initiatives are seen as having a limited impact.

- With the NEB programme aiming at encouraging small and medium scale citizen engagement projects, the absorption of direct funds is not the main challenge but rather the long-term sustainability of the incentivised initiative.
- In order to maintain and enhance outcomes, measures must be taken both horizontally for coherence across member states and vertically in order to fill in the gap that was identified by participants in the Digital Focus Groups regarding the visibility of the programme in the majority of citizens, that represents the largest part of the envisioned stakeholders of the NEB.

Digital Skills, Education and learning gaps

- The educational sector faces particular challenges. Uptake of novel technologies puts a pressure on lecturers to acquire the knowledge needed in order to embed the technology in their teachings.
- Digital solutions are intensively used in the education sector, but traditional learning –with analogue solutions– is considered essential for the development of critical thinking in the architecture and built environment programmes. Even if digital skills are faster acquired by the younger population, this comes with a warning from the educator’s side on the dangers that lack of critical thinking might bring with itself. Analogue learning has a forming experience.
- Low levels of literacy of the target population make it difficult to implement digital solutions. The competition with the private sector for digital skills is another challenge that members of civil society face.
- Knowledge and expertise of digitalisation accumulates yearly and thus it is expected that digitalisation levels will increase. However, in order to allow for social inclusion and accommodate all digital literacy levels, service providers, public and civic organisations interacting with the general public must also offer analogue solutions.
- Educational programs dedicated to AI are lacking in both volume and levels of adaptation.
- The need for critical thinking and questioning of the AI-enabled output should be an essential part of AI literacy programmes.

Digitalisation, the Green Deal objectives and Bio-based materials gaps

- Horizon Europe addresses the green transition through financially supporting research projects. However, at project level initiatives are ephemerally lived and rather perceived as research activities that are disengaged from the real work environment.
- There is a (perceived) gap on knowledge and training on the use of bio-based materials.
- The lack of standards brings additional challenges for insurance purposes, adding to the reticence of acceptance. Therefore, initiatives for encouraging use of bio-based materials don’t have to be limited to financial ones, but can also include initiatives for simplifying regulatory processes.

3. NEB Academy

Considering the lessons from the Observatory and Toolkit and taking the gap analysis to heart, it makes good sense to include the eLearning/training component of DigiNEB into the approach. Digital literacy and AI literacy were identified as key challenges together with a lacking ability to find, select and combine the use of different tools. As three out of four digiNEB partners continue their work in the New European Bauhaus Academy Alliance, the NEB Academy sets the stage for a perfect...

“long-term sustainability approach by ensuring that all methods and instruments are transferred to the relevant stakeholder groups for continued use.”

The link between DigiNEB and the NEB Academy doesn't come out of the blue. Early on in the DigiNEB project, the consortium was asked if it could provide the platform for hosting the NEB Academy, an initiative launched by EU President Ursula von der Leyen.

Things moved rather quickly though: late 2023, the idea of the NEB Academy evolved into an open call for a consortium that could prepare the launch of the NEB Academy.

The NEB Academy aims to accelerate **“up-skilling and re-skilling in the construction ecosystem, to support the transition from an extractive, mineral-based and fossil hydrocarbon-fueled construction economy, to a regenerative bio-economy and circular system of material reuse.”** [6]

The proposal by the New European Bauhaus Academy Alliance (led by the University of Primorska) was selected early in 2024. This Alliance will lay the foundation of a NEB training and skilling initiative, focussing on:

Bio-based - Using renewable, natural materials like wood, hemp, or straw in construction, promoting sustainability, reducing carbon footprints, and enhancing environmental resilience and resource efficiency.

Circular - Designing structures with reusable, recyclable materials, minimizing waste, and extending building lifecycles to promote sustainability and resource efficiency in construction.

Regenerative - Using renewable, natural materials like wood, hemp, or straw in construction, promoting sustainability, reducing carbon footprints, and enhancing environmental resilience and resource efficiency.

Long Life - prioritizing durability, adaptability, and resilience, designing structures that last through generations.

Digital - The use of digital tools to optimise design, planning, construction and maintenance.

4. Policy Context

The policy context of the DigiNEB roadmap is first of all set by the New European Bauhaus initiative.

New European Bauhaus (NEB)

“The New European Bauhaus (NEB) is a policy and funding initiative that makes green transition in built environments enjoyable, attractive and convenient for all. Even the smallest communities on the ground deserve living spaces that improve their well-being and sense of belonging.” [7]

Open Education

As part of the development towards open science, there is a growing awareness that open education is essential for creating equity or societal justice, not just for classroom or campus education but for lifelong learning as well. This means that the NEB Academy needs to take a closer look at the concept of Open Education.

The European Commission's definition of open education is:

“a way of carrying out education, often using digital technologies. Its aim is to widen access and participation to everyone by removing barriers and making learning accessible, abundant, and customisable for all. It offers multiple ways of teaching and learning, building and sharing knowledge. It also provides a variety of access routes to formal and non-formal education, and connects”

(Opening up Education: A Support Framework for Higher Education Institutions, 2016 [8])

The Commission stipulates the advantages of Open Education as:

- *First, it can help to reduce or remove barriers to education (e.g. cost, geography, time, entry requirements). This gives learners the opportunity to up skill or re-skill at a lower or nearly no cost, and in a flexible way.*
- *Second, it supports the modernisation of higher education in Europe, since contemporary open education is largely carried out via digital technologies.*
- *Finally, it opens up the possibility of bridging non-formal and formal education. This can take place if HE institutions and other accredited institutions recognised the credentials they each issue to learners. [9]*

In open science programmes in academia more advantages are mentioned, such as:

- Open Education opens up the opportunity to jointly develop educational resources by remixing, transforming, and building upon shared materials.
- Open Education provides the opportunity for educators to gain recognition when the open educational resources that they have created are used by an increasing community of learners throughout Europe.

Opening up education is a process of cultural change, and that may take time. Not every organisation is immediately ready to take this step into the unknown. Enforcing ‘open education’ could stifle a project or initiative. Stimulating and facilitating is a better approach. The educational support systems we put in place today should provide the option to share resources and be ready to facilitate open practices.

AEC sector / ECTP / B4P

The ambition of enabling ‘Europe’s Green Deal’ requires that we focus on a broader audience than just the NEB community. This is reflected in the EC’s definition of the NEB Academy, which specifically refers to the ‘construction ecosystem’. It implies that the full architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) sector participates, not just designers, planners, policymakers, and citizens, but also developers, investors, carpenters, and bricklayers.

In this sense NEB and the NEB Academy should take note of the initiatives launched by the European Construction Technology Platform (ECTP), especially those developed through the Built4People (B4P) Co-Programmed Partnership.

Local and European

Typically, designers, planners, policymakers, and citizens work locally or nationally. The architectural design sector, for instance, obtains only a small percentage of its revenue abroad. This is due to the required detailed knowledge of national or regional rules and regulations, and to local client-designer relations.

Construction workers, on the other hand, display a high level of mobility due to labour shortages and wage differences between various European countries. Skills obtained in Bulgaria or Poland should be recognised in the Netherlands or Denmark, and vice versa. The fact that vocational training is typically provided in national languages adds another requirement to a training programme as envisioned by the NEB Academy.

Architect – a protected profession

Although we need to look broader than just designers or architects, the architect does hold a key position in the construction ecosystem. Ensuring that architects are trained in digital skills and become digitally literate is essential.

The title of architect, however, is protected by the European Directive on the Recognition of Professional Qualifications. This necessitates that each member state registers who is qualified to call themselves an architect, based on training requirements that are formulated in official national regulations. If we aim for European schools and universities to embed digital literacy in their curricula, one way is to make it a binding requirement for obtaining the title.

The national scope of open education repositories

To implement the concept of open education requires a dedicated infrastructure where educators and trainers can upload, share, and download so-called Open Educational Resources (OER). Such facilities or repositories are being set up throughout Europe, but once more on a national or institutional level. Take, for instance, “**Edusources**” developed by SURF in the Netherlands, which describes itself as:

“the platform for digital (open) educational resources for Dutch education. The one-stop-shop with both educational resources and knowledge about creating, sharing, finding, and reusing digital educational resources.” [10]

The platform is provided by means of an institutional login procedure and can be used by all Dutch universities, universities of applied sciences, and vocational training institutions, but not by other Dutch training providers or by institutes elsewhere in Europe. This means that such national initiatives cannot yet be used for a broad European initiative like the NEB Academy. Additional solutions are required.

Life Long Learning, certificates and badges

The NEB Academy responds to the fact that learning doesn't stop after leaving school or college. As society, the economy, and technology keep evolving, it is necessary to update previously acquired knowledge and learn new skills. To effectively offer courses or training, we need a European system that recognizes the skills and knowledge obtained in these trainings by means of so-called micro-credentials and badges, issued by accredited educational institutes (e.g., members of the European Association for Architectural Education) or professional organisations (e.g., members of the Architects' Council of Europe).

Robust funding

A broader implementation of lifelong learning requires that member states officially integrate lifelong learning into their policies and the ways they finance education, just like the vocational, bachelor and master education and training offered to young adults.

5. Challenges

The main challenges from the DigiNEB digital tools and projects are:

- Fragmentation of initiatives/tools/projects;
- Discoverability of initiatives/tools/projects;
- Interoperability;
- Software accessibility (including costs).
- Weak implementation of open science/open-source;
- EU programs are not easily accessible for small developers;

The main challenges for the training/E-learning (NEB Academy) are:

- Fragmentation of course offerings
- Repositories for Open Educational Resources are developed institutionally/nationally
- Lack of E-learning adequate platform(s) for NEB lifelong learning;
- Integration of digital literacy and AI literacy in curricula;
- Certification of completed education/training;
- Transferability of the proof of acquired skills;
- Financing mechanism of lifelong learning.

From this we suggest two roadmaps, one for digitalisation, the other that should help developing the required level of digital literacy in the NEB/AEC ecosystem. The two roadmaps are closely linked to each other and can in fact support the development of the NEB Academy.

6. Roadmap digital literacy NEB

NEB course base

The New European Bauhaus Academy will be the first stop to collect, supervise and develop courses and trainings. Given the size of the European Union and the demand to support the Green Transition, it is likely that there will be many more solid courses or training options beyond the NEB Academy. Setting up and maintaining a certified register of course/training options, should resolve the current fragmentation of offerings.

EU dataspace for Open Educational Resources

Accelerating sharing, mixing and reusing of open educational resources (OER) within the European Union requires an infrastructure or dataspace dedicated to OER, being able to harvest from national or institutional collections, a repository that allows for the seamless integration of these resources in Learning Management Systems locally.

Integration of digital literacy and AI literacy in curricula

The title of architect is protected in the EU while the entry terms to register as such are recorded in national regulations. Higher education institutions should include digital and AI literacy in their curricula, considering it essential for the accreditation of the degree and the registration of the professional title. Alternatively, a bottom-up push can be facilitated through leading institutes of higher education, its associations (EAAE, AESOP). Working with the Architect's Council Europe (ACE), is another option. Most of the national registration entities offers access to life-long learning through the ACE.

EU micro-credentials

Lifelong learning will use so-called micro-credentials (in the range of 3 – 30 ECTS) to award the completion of a course or training. Various EU countries have already piloted with these micro-credentials. Given the high level of mobility, especially among construction workers in the AEC, a European standard or implementation is required, similar to the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS).

Open Badges / EuroPass

Assuming a well-functioning EU-wide system for micro-credentials is in place, then those that have acquired micro-credentials should be provided with proof (certification) of this. EuroPass is one possibility but there are also digital Open Badge systems available that can provide this. The European Commission should develop or choose a standard.

Financing mechanism of lifelong learning (LLL finance).

Each of the EU countries have a financial mechanism in place that facilitate the education of young adults whether they participate in vocational, bachelor or master education. A similar mechanism needs to be implemented to finance lifelong learning.

Course localisation

Acknowledging that the EU embraces open education, EU countries should provide support for translating excellent courses or trainings from one language into the next local EU language, to adapt them to national or regional specifications and to facilitate that these courses or trainings are provided locally.

Timeline of recommendations to the European Commission.

2025-2030

NEB course base

EU dataspace for Open Educational Resources

Open Badges / EuroPass: the Badges work in tandem with the EU-wide rollout of the EU micro-credentials. A single system or procedure however is easier to implement than a coordination of 27 member states.

2030-2035

EU wide implementation of micro-credentials for lifelong learning

Timeline of recommendations to the EU member states

2020-2025

OER repositories at national or institutional level

Micro-credential pilots throughout Europe

2025-2030

The fact that vocational training is typically provided in national languages adds another requirement to a training programme as envisioned by the NEB Academy.

The commission is advised to provide funding to its members for course localisation to adapt trainings to regional languages, conditions, materials and practices throughout the EU.

Pilots with new funding mechanisms for lifelong learning in various member states.

2030-2035

Funding principles for lifelong learning.

7. Roadmap digitalisation NEB

Cascading NEB grants;

The NEB community consist of many relatively small organisations or enterprises that are poorly represented in EU-funded project proposals. The commission should apply its cascading funding scheme to partners in the NEB community that have the oversight to organise the sector: partners like the NEB Collective, the NEB Labs, Innovawood, EAAE and ACE. These organisations have the capacity to organize target calls in-line with the NEB framework.

Open-source requirement;

The commission should require that digital tools or solutions funded through EU-programming become always available as open-source, unless knowledge security (dual-use) requires otherwise.

Support for the open-source development of adequate E-learning and citizen's platform(s)

To facilitate collaboration and lifelong learning, the Commission is advised to fast track the development of emerging platforms for E-learning and citizens (local democracy/co-planning/design), under the condition that work is available as open-source solution.

Digital workflows;

Next to the development of digital tools and solutions there is a need for the development (and teaching) of workflows based on multiple tools and solutions. It means that the method or the methodology of using existing tools in novel combinations for specific functions or objectives should become a focus in EU-programming, next to the development of such tools themselves.

Discovery support;

The return on investment in EU-programming may increase drastically if EU-programs are not just confined to providing money and monitoring, but if they support actively the dissemination of the projects, the training participants how to do outreach, ensuring that others are trained how to use the tools, and that partners build networks with local and regional governments, market parties, NGOs. The European Commission could expand its programs to provide the resources for activities focused on discovery. The execution of such an approach is probably most effective when it is locally or nationally organised.

Horizon software space;

The commission needs to set up a Git repository where projects are required to host and develop their digital solutions for use, reuse and further development.

Interoperability;

Many EU projects develop tools that are good in one thing, and one thing only, for example energy-efficiency. The European Commission needs to require that its funded projects address the full complexity of “beautiful, sustainable and together”.

Timeline of recommendations to the European Commission.

2020-2025

DigiNEB start

2025-2030

Cascading NEB grants;

Open-source development of adequate E-learning and citizen’s platform(s);

Open-source and interoperability requirement for EU-funded digital projects;

2030-2035

Focus on digital workflows;

Horizon software space.

Timeline of recommendations to the EU member states

2025-2030

Open-source development of adequate E-learning and citizen’s platform(s);

2030-2035

Providing discovery support.

Figure 2 – DigiNEB Road map.

8. Conclusion

The DigiNEB project, aligned with the New European Bauhaus (NEB) initiative, represents a pivotal step in bridging the digital and green transitions within the built environment. By fostering a pan-European digital ecosystem, DigiNEB aims to make the green transition enjoyable, attractive, and accessible for all stakeholders. The project's focus on digital tools, observatories, and gap analyses highlights critical challenges, including funding mismatches, accessibility issues, and the need for interoperability and long-term sustainability of digital solutions. These gaps underscore the necessity for a more inclusive and cohesive approach to digital innovation, particularly for smaller enterprises and micro-developers who struggle to align with large-scale EU funding programs.

The integration of the NEB Academy into DigiNEB's framework further emphasizes the importance of digital and AI literacy in achieving the Green Deal's ambitions. By addressing educational gaps and promoting lifelong learning through micro-credentials and open educational resources, the NEB Academy can empower the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) sector to adopt sustainable practices. However, challenges such as fragmented course offerings, national barriers to open education, and the need for robust funding mechanisms for lifelong learning must be addressed to ensure the initiative's success.

The proposed roadmaps for digital literacy and digitalisation provide a clear pathway for overcoming these challenges. Recommendations such as cascading NEB grants, open-source requirements, and the development of digital workflows and discovery support systems are essential for fostering innovation and collaboration.

By addressing gaps in funding, accessibility, interoperability, and digital skills, these roadmaps will support the EU's Green Deal and ensure the long-term success of the NEB initiative through the continuation in the NEB Academy. The integration of open education, micro-credentials, and open-source solutions will empower stakeholders to drive the green transition effectively.

Figure 3 – DigiNEB Road map, larger version.

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Positioning the digital projects/tools on two axes: openness and developer size.

Figure 2 – DigNEB Road map.

Figure 3 – DigNEB Road map, larger version.

References

[1] <https://digiNEB.eu/digineb-project>

[2], [3] GRANT AGREEMENT Project 101083743 — digiNEB.eu

[4] Deliverable D2.3 – Landscape report and gap analysis – preliminary version

[5] Deliverable D2.5 – Landscape report and gap analysis – final version

[6] https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/about/NEB-academy_en

[7] https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

[8] <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC101436>

[9] https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/what-open-education_en

[10] <https://edusources.nl>

